

10. Stirling W. D. Textbooks for Learning Statistics: Public CAST e-books. 2013.

URL: http://cast.massey.ac.nz/collection_public.html.

11. The Fluid Aspect of the Mediterranean Diet in the Prevention and Management of Cardiovascular Disease and Diabetes: The Role of Polyphenol Content in Moderate Consumption of Wine and Olive Oil / P. Ditano-Vázquez et al. *Nutrients*. 2019. Vol. 11, No. 11. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu11112833>

12. The relationship between oxidative stress markers and visual evoked potentials in different hypertension

models / A. Y. Göçmen et al. *Anadolu Kardiyol. Derg.* 2014. Vol. 14, No. 6. P. 498-504.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5152/akd.2014.4923>

13. Whelton P. K. 2017 ACC/AHA/AAPA/ABC/ACPM/ AGS/ APhA/ ASH/ ASPC/ NMA/ PCNA Guideline for the Prevention, Detection, Evaluation, and Management of High Blood Pressure in Adults: Executive Summary: A Report of the American College of Cardiology/American Heart Association Task Force on Clinical Practice Guidelines. *Hypertension*. 2018. Vol. 71. P. 1269-1324. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1161/HYP.0000000000000066>

The article was received
2019.12.13

UDC 616.329-002-008.6+616.441-002]-092:612.015.1

<https://doi.org/10.26641/2307-0404.2020.4.221237>

O.M. Kovalyova¹,
N.D. Chukhrienko²,
T.M. Pasiyeshvili¹,
L.M. Pasiyeshvili¹,
N.M. Zhelezniakova¹

THE STATE OF ANTIOXIDANT DEFENSE SYSTEM IN YOUNG PERSONS WITH GASTROESOPHAGEAL REFLUX DISEASE AND AUTOIMMUNE THYROIDITIS

*Kharkiv National Medical University, Ukraine*¹

Department of General Practice - Family Medicine and Internal Diseases

Nauky av., 4, Kharkiv, 61022, Ukraine

*SE «Dnipropetrovsk medical academy of Health Ministry of Ukraine»*²

Department of Family Medicine

V. Vernadsky str., 9, Dnipro, 49044, Ukraine

*Харківський національний медичний університет, Україна*¹

кафедра загальної практики - сімейної медицини та внутрішніх хвороб

(зав. – д. мед. н., проф. Л.М. Пасієшвілі)

пр. Науки, 4, Харків, 61022, Україна

*ДЗ «Дніпропетровська медична академія МОЗ України»*²

кафедра сімейної медицини

(зав. – д. мед. н., проф. І.Л. Височина)

вул. В. Вернадського, 9, Дніпро, 49044, Україна

e-mail: prokov@gmail.com

Цитування: *Медичні перспективи*. 2020. Т. 25, № 4. С. 87-93

Cited: *Medicni perspektivi*. 2020;25(4):87-93

Key words: *gastroesophageal reflux disease, autoimmune thyroiditis, total antioxidant activity, manganese superoxide dismutase, Klotho protein*

Ключові слова: *гастроезофагеальна рефлюксна хвороба, автоімунний тиреоїдит, загальна антиоксидантна активність, марганець супероксиддисмутаза, протеїн Клото*

Ключевые слова: *гастрозофагеальная рефлюксная болезнь, аутоиммунный тиреоидит, общая антиоксидантная активность, марганец супероксиддисмутаза, протеин Клото*

Abstract. *The state of antioxidant defense system in young persons with gastroesophageal reflux disease and autoimmune thyroiditis. Kovalyova O.M., Chukhrienko N.D., Pasiyeshvili T.M., Pasiyeshvili L.M., Zhelezniakova N.M. Aim of research was assessment of the levels of antioxidant biomarkers associated with mitochondrial function in young patients with gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD) and autoimmune thyroiditis*

(AIT). This study included 165 patients of them 120 patients with GERD and AIT - the main group, 45 patients with isolated GERD - the comparison group. The examined contingent was presented by students aged 18 to 25 years. The control group consisted of 20 healthy individuals of corresponding gender, age and social status (students). Total antioxidant activity (TAS-TAC) was determined in blood serum of study persons with enzyme immunoassays (ELISA, Elabscience, USA), levels of manganese superoxide dismutase (MnSOD) – with enzyme immunoassays (ELISA, Elabscience, USA) and Klotho protein - with enzyme immunoassays (ELISA, Elabscience, USA). Statistical data processing by the Statistica Basic Academic 13 for Windows En local was made. In examined patients with esophageal and thyroid pathologies the decline of total antioxidant activity has been revealed. The MnSOD level in patients with comorbidity of GERD and AIT and isolated GERD was significantly higher as compare to control group. Significant increasing of Klotho protein in serum of young patients was observed. We assessed imbalance between decline of extracellular antioxidants and activation of mitochondrial antioxidants which is more pronounced in combination of diseases. The increase of biomarkers of mitochondrial antioxidant defense system with non-specific citoprotection mechanism in patients with GERD provides the basis to consider MnSOD and Klotho protein as prognostic indicator of clinical outcome of disease in young age. Under combination of GERD and AIT the tendency to overexpression of MnSOD and depression of total antioxidant activity has been revealed, this may cause the deterioration of mitochondrial function.

Реферат. Стан антиоксидантної системи в молодих пацієнтів з гастроєзофагеальною рефлюксною хворобою та аутоімунним тиреоїдитом. Ковальова О.М., Чухрієнко Н.Д., Пасієшвілі Т.М., Пасієшвілі Л.М., Железнякова Н.М. Метою дослідження було визначення в пацієнтів молодого віку з гастроєзофагеальною рефлюксною хворобою (ГЕРХ) та аутоімунним тиреоїдитом (АІТ) рівня антиоксидантних біомаркерів, що асоціюються з функцією мітохондрій. Дослідження включало 165 хворих, серед яких 120 хворих з ГЕРХ і АІТ-основна група, 45 хворих з ізольованою ГЕРХ – група порівняння. Досліджуваній контингент представлено студентами у віці від 18 до 25 років. Контрольну групу склали 20 здорових осіб, що відповідали за статтю, віком та соціальним статусом (студенти). Загальна антиоксидантна активність (TAS-TAC) у сироватці крові досліджуваних визначалась імуноферментним методом з використанням тест-системи (ELISA, Elabscience, США), рівень марганцю супероксиддисмутази (MnSOD) – імуноферментним методом (ELISA, Elabscience, США), рівень протеїна Клото (Klotho protein) - імуноферментним методом (ELISA, Elabscience, США). Статистичний аналіз результатів дослідження було проведено за допомогою системи Statistica Basic Academic 13 for Windows En локальна. У досліджених хворих з патологією стравоходу та щитоподібної залози визначено зниження загальної антиоксидантної активності порівняно зі здоровими особами. Рівень марганцю супероксиддисмутази у хворих з коморбідним перебігом ГЕРХ та АІТ та хворих з ізольованою ГЕРХ достовірно перевищував показники контрольної групи. Відзначається достовірне збільшення рівня протеїну Клото в сироватці крові хворих молодого віку. Встановлено дисбаланс між ступенем зниження позаклітинних антиоксидантів та активацією мітохондріального антиоксиданта, що найбільш виражено у хворих при сполученні захворювань. Підвищення у хворих маркерів мітохондріального антиоксидантного захисту з неспецифічним механізмом цитопротекції дає підставу для використання марганцю супероксиддисмутази та протеїну Клото як прогностичних індикаторів клінічного перебігу захворювання в молодому віці. При коморбідності ГЕРХ та АІТ встановлена тенденція до значного підвищення продукції марганцю супероксиддисмутази на фоні зниження загального антиоксидантного захисту, що може призводити до погіршення мітохондріальної функції.

Modern clinic of internal medicine is characterized by comorbidity which means the combination of some diseases in one patient. Among these diseases gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD) and autoimmune thyroiditis (AIT) are ranked as the most common diagnoses in outpatient care.

The spreading of GERD is tremendously increasing worldwide resulting in adverse medical and economic consequences, its impact on healthcare cost is reported to be extremely high [5]. The symptoms of GERD may appear in young age as dangerous prognostic feature of more serious condition in future known as Barrett's esophagus. Another disease that often occurs at a young age is AIT. Both diseases may result from a multifactorial mechanisms with general pathological process related to the classical laws of inflammation.

Systemic inflammatory response syndrome of non-infection origin has recently come to be recognized as a fundamental clinical problem due to wide involving in pathogenesis of numerous diseases. Under condition of inflammation overproduction of reactive oxygen species (ROS) appear, thus a lot of diseases of internal organs are accompanied by formation of oxidative stress with damage to the biological macromolecules and cell membranes [11]. Synthesis of thyroid hormones and regulation of their metabolism involve free radicals that may affect redox balance in the body. Thyroid disorders causing variations in the levels of thyroid hormones may alter cellular oxidative stress [2].

The human body has several mechanisms to counteract oxidative stress by producing endogenous antioxidants which act as “free radical scavengers”

by preventing and repairing damages caused by ROS [10]. The important center for the metabolic activities of the body that involves ROS production is mitochondria [3]. Due to the chronic excessive ROS in mitochondria resulted from inflammation, the affection of mitochondrial DNA starts as well as direct damage to cell structure and function [7].

Mitochondria are not only the main sites of ROS production but also important organelles in the antioxidant system. The major ROS detoxifying enzyme of cells localized in mitochondria is superoxide dismutase (SOD) which is a metalloenzyme and hence, requires a metal cofactor for its activity named manganese superoxide dismutase (MnSOD) [14]. An important role in maintaining antioxidant defence during H₂O₂-induced oxidative stress plays newly discovered Klotho protein [15].

Nevertheless in previous studies there are insufficient data relevant to mitochondrial antioxidant defense system in patients with gastrointestinal disorders and thyroid disease. In order to clarify this problem we selected MnSOD and Klotho protein in blood serum of young persons as indicators of mitochondrial antioxidant system.

The purpose: assessment of the state of antioxidant defense system in young patients with GERD and AIT based on activity of biomarkers associated with mitochondrial function.

MATERIALS AND METHODS OF RESEARCH

This study included 165 patients, of them 120 patients with GERD and AIT – the main group, 45 patients with isolated GERD – the comparison group. The examined contingent was presented by university students aged 18 to 25 years. Median age in main group was 21.9±2.7 years and 21.2±2.4 years in comparison group; 93 patients (77.5%) in group with GERD and AIT and 34 patients (75.6%) with isolated GERD were women, 27 (22.5%) and 11 (24.4%) were men. The anamnesis of GERD and AIT did not exceed 3 years. The control group consisted of 20 healthy individuals, corresponding to gender, age and social status (students).

This research was conducted in compliance with all relevant diagnostic and treatment standards of the requirements for the ethical component of clinical trials (GCP, 1997). Before the study, patients were informed about the essence of the study, its purpose and possible results. All study participants provided written informed consent. This study was approved by the local ethics committee according to the recommendations of the ethical committees for biomedical research, Ukrainian legislation on health protection, the 2000 Helsinki Declaration and the directives of the European Partnership 86/609 on the participation of people in biomedical research.

Verification of the GERD diagnosis was performed according to the recommendation of the Montreal Consensus (2006), “Protocols for the management of patients ...” with this nosology and ICD-10”. The morphological form of the disease was revealed during esophagogastroduodenoscopy («Fuginon» system, Japan) according to the recommendations of the Los Angeles classification.

Verification of AIT was performed on the basis of data from an ultrasound examination of the thyroid gland (Mindray DC-60 Exp, China) and evaluation of test results for antibodies to thyroid peroxidase and thyroglobulin; thyroid function was assessed by the levels of thyroid stimulating hormone, thyroxine and triiodothyronine. Euthyroid state was in all cases of autoimmune thyroiditis.

Total Antioxidant Activity (Total Antioxidant Status and Total Antioxidant Capacity – TAS-TAC) was determined in blood serum of study persons with enzyme immunoassays (ELISA, Elabscience, USA) analyzer Labline-80. Levels of MnSOD in blood serum were determined with enzyme immunoassay analyzer Labline-90 (ELISA, Elabscience USA) and Klotho protein was determined in blood serum with enzyme immunoassay using a commercial test system manufactured by Elabscience (ELISA, USA) according to the instructions attached to the kit.

Statistical data processing was made by the Statistica Basic Academic 13 for Windows En local general-purpose software package (License Number: 139-956-866). The significance of differences was calculated using the Student's test (t). The relationship between the studied parameters was assessed using the Pearson correlation analysis (r). The critical level of statistical significance in checking all hypotheses was taken at <5% (p<0.05) [1].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Total antioxidant activity in blood serum of study patients and control persons is presented in Table 1.

The present study demonstrates that patients with GERD and AIT and patients with isolated GERD have decreased levels of total antioxidant activity as compared to persons of control group. The total antioxidant activity in GERD and AIT patients was lower than in patients with isolated GERD, the difference is statistically significant between groups.

The levels of MnSOD in blood serum of study patients and control persons are presented in Figure 1.

Patients had significantly higher serum levels of MnSOD compared to control persons. In patients with combined course of GERD and AIT mediana and interpercentil deviation of MnSOD was 9.1965 (7.2480; 11.6385) ng/ml which is two times higher than the control indices – 4.4720 (3.7010;

5.2325) ng/ml (U=386, p<0.01), and significantly exceeded the indices of the comparison group (7.1700 (6.1056; 8.1948) ng/ml (U=108, p<0.01). The indices

of the group with isolated GERD also exceeded the indices of the control group. (U=276, p<0.01).

Table 1

Total antioxidant activity (TAS-TAC) of study patients and control persons

Patients/ indicators	TAS-TAC, $\mu\text{mol/l}$	Significance of differences compared with control group*	Significance of differences between groups*
GERD and AIT	305.2570 (160.1890; 425.1080)	U=376 p<0.01	U=1557 p<0.01
GERD	439.4680 (311.5332; 585.6220)	U=284.5 p<0.01	
Control group	517.8108 (419.1486; 809.2243)		

Note. *p<0.05 – the difference is statistically significant between groups.

The levels of Klotho protein in blood serum of study patients and control persons are presented in Figure 2.

Klotho protein levels was significantly higher in both study groups of patients compared to healthy individuals (0.4958 (0.3679; 0.6098) ng/ml). In group with isolated GERD it was 0.6130 (0.4612; 0.7630) ng/ml (U=279.5, p<0.01). Levels of Klotho protein in group with comorbidity GERD and AIT were 0.8070 (0.6110; 1.1840) ng/ml and exceeded levels of the control group (U=320.5, p<0.01) and of the comparison group (U=1570, p<0.01). We found direct correlation between the levels Klotho protein and MnSOD in the main group (r=0.724).

According to presented data in young patients with GERD and AIT total antioxidant activity decreases which is primarily extracellular chain antioxidant representing the functional sum of antioxidants in plasma [8].

Total antioxidant activity is one of the feature of oxidative stress defined as an imbalance between radicals and antioxidant defense and is involved into pathophysiological mechanism of different diseases. Previously studies suggested that inflammatory cytokines and oxidative stress induced by the mixed reflux of gastric acid and duodenal juice play an important role in the development of esophagitis [13].

Fig. 1. Levels of MnSOD in patients of study and control group

Fig. 2. Levels of Klotho protein in individuals of study and control groups

Oxidative stress can be related to hormonal disturbances due to the modification of synthesis, activity and metabolism of thyroid hormones. Thyroid disorders cause influence of the levels of antioxidant status, decline capability to prevent oxidative stress [12].

Thus, in our study we showed that the comorbidity of GERD and AIT in patients causes the failure of the extracellular phase of the antioxidant defense and various decline of control over the toxic radicals. It is known that stressors not only damage epithelial cells, but also causes free radical generation in their mitochondria causing dramatic effects on cellular function, organ injury and disturbance. [4].

High serum levels of MnSOD in patients of both studied group significantly exceeded the levels in control group patients. These data relevant to activation of intracellular antioxidant system seem to be an adaptive response to suppression of extracellular antioxidant system in patients with esophagitis and thyroiditis. MnSOD regulates mitochondrial function by decreasing ROS production, protect from pro-oxidant and pro-apoptotic stimuli as well as from ischemic damage [6, 9].

Recently it has been revealed that increased activities of antioxidant enzymes (superoxide dismutase, catalase and heme oxygenase-1) may be due to Klotho protein which induces the expression of the manganese superoxide dismutase and acts as ROS scavenger, poses antioxidant and anti-apoptotic effects in response to oxidative damage to cells, inhibits TNF- α , IL-6 [15, 16].

As a result of our study we have received the parallel increasing the levels of mitochondrial SOD and Klotho protein in blood serum in the group of patients with comorbidity and isolated pathology as compared to control group. Correlation between MnSOD and Klotho protein confirmed the participation of Klotho protein in antioxidant system due to stimulation of which resistance to oxidative stress increases and cytoprotection is provided.

Based on experimental and clinical studies it is known that expression of MnSOD provides positive effect and protects of a variety of cell lines from oxidative stress in case of adequate activity of antioxidant enzyme like superoxide dismutase, catalase and glutathione peroxidase which can prevent oxidation by reducing the rate of chain initiation. On the other hand in certain circumstances in reduced extracellular antioxidant activity MnSOD may lose their antioxidative ability and even act as a pro-oxidant which can generate toxic reactive oxygen forms, may work as a peroxidase, using H₂O₂- to promote mitochondrial damage.

CONCLUSIONS

1. An isolated gastroesophageal reflux disease and its combination with the autoimmune thyroiditis is accompanied by a decrease in total antioxidant activity and an increase in MnSOD levels.

2. Gastroesophageal reflux disease and autoimmune thyroiditis in young patients is accompanied with elevation of Klotho protein in blood serum which is responsible for activation of the antioxidant

enzyme of manganese superoxide dismutase and hence increases resistance to oxidative stress and provides cytoprotection.

3. The imbalance between extracellular and intracellular antioxidant defense system is more pronounced in patients with gastroesophageal reflux disease and autoimmune thyroiditis.

4. Thyroid disorders that accompany gastroesophageal reflux disease are characterized by the tendency to MnSOD overexpression, which may have negative effects.

Conflict of interests. The authors declare no conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

1. Antomonov MYu. [Mathematical processing and analysis of biomedical data]. *Medinform*. 2018;579. Russian.
2. Ramli NSF, Mat Junit S, Leong NK, Razali N, Jayapalan JJ, Abdul Aziz A. Analyses of antioxidant status and nucleotide alterations in genes encoding antioxidant enzymes in patients with benign and malignant thyroid disorders. *PeerJ*. 2017;5:e3365. Published 2017 Jun 1. doi: <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.3365>
3. Angelova PR, Abramov AY Functional role of mitochondrial reactive oxygen species in physiology. *Free Radic Biol Med*. 2016;100:81-85. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.freeradbiomed.2016.06.005>
4. He L, He T, Farrar S, Ji L, Liu T, Ma X. Antioxidants Maintain Cellular Redox Homeostasis by Elimination of Reactive Oxygen Species. *Cell Physiol Biochem* 2017;44:532-553. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1159/000485089>
5. Antunes C, Curtis SA. Gastroesophageal Reflux Disease. [Updated 2019 Sep 30]. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2020 Jan. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK441938/>
6. Chen Y, Zhou Z, Min W. Mitochondria, Oxidative Stress and Innate Immunity. *Front Physiol*. 2018;9:1487. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphys.2018.01487>
7. Ding N, Maiuri AR, O'Hagan HM. The emerging role of epigenetic modifiers in repair of DNA damage associated with chronic inflammatory diseases. *Mutat Res*. 2019;780:69-81. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mrrev.2017.09.005>
8. Kurutas EB. The importance of antioxidants which play the role in cellular response against oxidative/nitrosative stress: current state. *Nutr J*. 2016;15(1):71. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12937-016-0186-5>
9. Kitada M, Xu J, Ogura Y, Monno I and Koya D. Manganese Superoxide Dismutase Dysfunction and the Pathogenesis of Kidney Disease. *Front. Physiol*. 2020;11:755. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphys.2020.00755>
10. Ahmadinejad F, Geir Møller S, Hashemzadeh-Chaleshtori M, Bidkhorji G, Jami MS. Molecular Mechanisms behind Free Radical Scavengers Function against Oxidative Stress. *Antioxidants (Basel)*. 2017;6(3):51. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/antiox6030051>
11. Hussain T, Tan B, Yin Y, Blachier F, Tossou MC, Rahu N. Oxidative Stress and Inflammation: What Polyphenols Can Do for Us? *Oxid Med Cell Longev*. 2016;2016:7432797. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1155/2016/7432797>
12. Chakrabarti SK, Ghosh S, Banerjee S, Mukherjee S, Chowdhury S. Oxidative stress in hypothyroid patients and the role of antioxidant supplementation. *Indian J Endocrinol Metab*. 2016;20(5):674-678. doi: <https://doi.org/10.4103/2230-8210.190555>
13. Yoshida N, Imamura Y, Baba Y, et al. Pathogenesis of acute gastroesophageal reflux disease might be changing. *Transl Cancer Res* 2016;5(4):645-647. doi: <https://doi.org/10.21037/tcr.2016.10.57>
14. Snezhkina AV, Kudryavtseva AV, Kardymon OL, et al. ROS Generation and Antioxidant Defense Systems in Normal and Malignant Cells. *Oxid Med Cell Longev*. 2019;2019:6175804. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1155/2019/6175804>
15. Kimura T, Shiizaki K, Akimoto T. et al. The impact of preserved Klotho gene expression on antioxidative stress activity in healthy kidney. *Am J Physiol Renal Physiol* 2018;315:345-352. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1152/ajprenal.00486.2017>
16. Wei C, Wei BL, Pin WG. Klotho protein inhibits H₂O₂-induced oxidative injury in endothelial Cells via regulation of PI3K/Akt/Nrf2/HO-1 Pathways. *Canadian Journal of Physiology and Pharmacology* 2019;97(5):370-376, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1139/cjpp-2018-0277>

СПИСОК ЛІТЕРАТУРИ

1. Антомонов М. Ю. Математическая обработка и анализ медико-биологических данных. Киев: Мединформ, 2018. 579 с.
2. Analyses of antioxidant status and nucleotide alterations in genes encoding antioxidant enzymes in patients with benign and malignant thyroid disorders / N. S. F. Ramli et al. *Peer J*. 2017. Vol. 5. P. e3365. Published 2017 Jun 1. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.3365>
3. Angelova P. R., Abramov A. Y. Functional role of mitochondrial reactive oxygen species in physiology. *Free Radic Biol Med*. 2016. Vol. 100. P. 81-85. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.freeradbiomed.2016.06.005>
4. Antioxidants Maintain Cellular Redox Homeostasis by Elimination of Reactive Oxygen Species / L. He et al. *Cell Physiol Biochem*. 2017. Vol. 44. P. 532-553. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1159/000485089>

5. Antunes C, Curtis SA. Gastroesophageal Reflux Disease. Updated 2019 Sep 30. In: StatPearls. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing, 2020 Jan. URL: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK441938/>
6. Chen Y., Zhou Z., Min W. Mitochondria, Oxidative Stress and Innate Immunity. *Front Physiol.* 2018. Vol. 9. P. 1487. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphys.2018.01487>
7. Ding N., Maiuri A. R., O'Hagan H. M. The emerging role of epigenetic modifiers in repair of DNA damage associated with chronic inflammatory diseases. *Mutat Res.* 2019. Vol. 780. P. 69-81. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mrrev.2017.09.005>
8. Kurutas E. B. The importance of antioxidants which play the role in cellular response against oxidative/nitrosative stress: current state. *Nutr J.* 2016. Vol. 15, No. 1. P. 71. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12937-016-0186-5>
9. Manganese Superoxide Dismutase Dysfunction and the Pathogenesis of Kidney Disease / M. Kitada et al. *Front. Physiol.* 2020. Vol. 11. P. 755. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphys.2020.00755>
10. Molecular Mechanisms behind Free Radical Scavengers Function against Oxidative Stress. / F. Ahmadijad et al. *Antioxidants (Basel).* 2017. Vol. 6, No. 3. P. 51. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3390/antiox6030051>
11. Oxidative Stress and Inflammation: What Polyphenols Can Do for Us? / T. Hussain et al. *Oxid Med Cell Longev.* 2016. Vol. 2016. P. 7432797. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1155/2016/7432797>
12. Oxidative stress in hypothyroid patients and the role of antioxidant supplementation / S. K. Chakrabarti, et al. *Indian J Endocrinol Metab.* 2016. Vol. 20, No. 5. P. 674-678. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.4103/2230-8210.190555>
13. Pathogenesis of acute gastroesophageal reflux disease might be changing / N. Yoshida et al. *Transl Cancer Res.* 2016. Vol. 5, No. 4. P. 645-647. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.21037/tcr.2016.10.57>
14. ROS Generation and Antioxidant Defense Systems in Normal and Malignant Cells / A. V. Snezhkina et al. *Oxid Med Cell Longev.* 2019. Vol. 2019. P. 6175804. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1155/2019/6175804>
15. The impact of preserved Klotho gene expression on antioxidative stress activity in healthy kidney / T. Kimura et al. *Am J Physiol Renal Physiol.* 2018. Vol. 315. P. 345-352. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1152/ajprenal.00486.2017>
16. Wei C., Wei B. L., Pin W. G. Klotho protein inhibits H₂O₂-induced oxidative injury in endothelial Cells via regulation of PI3K/Akt/Nrf2/HO-1 Pathways. *Canadian Journal of Physiology and Pharmacology.* 2019. Vol. 97, No. 5. P. 370-376, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1139/cjpp-2018-0277>

The article was received
2020.09.21

